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Deployment of Antepsin (Sucralfate) as Corrosion Inhibitor of Mild Steel in H₂SO₄ Medium: Chemical and Electrochemical Studies

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the deployment of antepsin (sucralfate) as corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in H₂SO₄ medium. Chemical (gravimetric) and electrochemical (potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy) techniques were used in the corrosion control investigation. The antepsin drug was characterized by gas chromatography mass spectrophotometer (GCMS) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Effects of inhibitor concentration, temperature and time on weight loss, corrosion rate, inhibition efficiency and degree of surface coverage were examined. Thermodynamic and adsorption properties of the corrosion inhibition process were determined. Inhibition efficiency was optimized using central composite design tool of Design Expert software version 12. Potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy were employed to determine the type and effectiveness of the inhibitor. As a confirmatory test, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to examine the surface morphology of the mild steel samples. Analysis of the results showed that major constituents of antepsin include tetradecanoate, metronidazole, hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester and 11-octadecenoic acid. The predominant functional groups include; C=O stretch, C-H bend and symmetric and asymmetric =C-O-C. Adsorption of the molecules of antepsin on the surface of the mild steel was spontaneous and occurred in agreement with physical adsorption. A quadratic model adequately described the relationship between inhibition efficiency and corrosion control variables of concentration of the inhibitor, temperature and time. Optimum inhibition efficiency of antepsin was obtained as 86.75%. Chemical and electrochemical results agreed that antepsin is suitable for corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ solution. Antepsin acted as mixed-type inhibitor (controlled both cathodic and anodic reactions).

Keywords: Antepsin, Corrosion, H₂SO₄, Inhibitor, Mild Steel

1. INTRODUCTION

Mild steel is one of the most widely applied metals in engineering and allied industries [1, 2]. It is used in the fabrication of drums, pipes, reaction vessels and other related materials. Its usefulness is usually defied by corrosion. Corrosion causes enormous damage to mild steel structures; with corresponding economic, safety and environmental consequences. Researchers have identified various ways of controlling corrosion of metallic structures [3, 4].

Corrosion control process requires maintenance operations such as pickling and acid descaling. Pickling is a process of using aggressive solution (such as H₂SO₄) to dissolve oxide formation and other related materials on metal surface. Inhibitors are required in such H₂SO₄ medium in order to avert corrosion. Use of inhibitors has proven to be the easiest, cheapest and environmentally friendly technique for corrosion control [4-6]. Corrosion inhibitors enhance formation of a protective oxide film and/or inhibit corrosion by creating a barrier that prevents access of corrosive agents to the metal surface [8].

In various industrial applications, synthetic substances are often used as corrosion inhibitors [9, 10]. Despite the significance of inhibition efficiency of such synthetic substances, most of them are expensive and carcinogenic [11]. As a result of these limitations, efforts are made towards development of effective and eco-friendly corrosion inhibitors. Currently, emphasis is on identification, development and deployment of green corrosion inhibitors. There are several reports on the application of plant extracts and other related substances for corrosion control [12, 13]. And it has been observed that application of plant extract as corrosion inhibitor is restricted by lack of recipes for development of plant extract of proven safety data and variations in its chemical composition [14].

Consequently, there is need to employ pharmaceutical drugs as corrosion inhibitors. It will help to reduce incidences of expired drugs, due to diversification of its applications. Use of pharmaceutical drugs as corrosion inhibitors had been limited to antibacterial and anti-fungal drugs [15].

Thus, this study is aimed at studying antepsin drug as corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in H₂SO₄ medium. Antepsin is a drug for treating stomach ulcers, gastroesophageal reflux disease, radiation proctitis, stomach inflammation, as well as stress ulcer. It is necessary to widen its applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2. 1. Materials

Materials and reagents used this study include mild steel, distilled water, H₂SO₄ and antepsin (Sucralfate as chemical name). Equipment used in the study were Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (Cary 630, Agilent Technologies USA), gas chromatography-mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies model 7890A and 5977B MSD), potentiostat/galvanostat 263 electrochemical system workstation, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2. 2. Preparation of the Mild Steel and Characterization of Antepsin

The mild steel with composition of Mn (0.13%), P (0.22%), Si (0.05%), S (0.12%), C (0.24%), Cr (0.02%), Ni (0.07), and Fe (99.15 %) was cut into coupons (4 cm × 3 cm × 0.1 cm). The coupons were cleaned, polished with emery paper, degreased with acetone, washed with distilled water, and dried in air.

Chemical analysis of the antepsin was carried using gas chromatography-mass spectrophotometer. The method used is similar to that of previous authors [16, 17]. Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer was used for the determination of the functional groups of the antepsin.

2. 3. Gravimetric Method

Effects of individual corrosion control variables

Individual effects of inhibitor concentration, temperature and time on weight loss, corrosion rate, inhibition efficiency and degree of surface coverage were studied [7, 17, 18].

2. 4. Adsorption isotherms of the corrosion inhibition

Langmuir, Frumkin, Temkin and Flory-Huggins adsorption isotherms of Eq. (1), (2), (3) and (4) respectively were used to test the adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface [7, 18]. The free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) was calculated using Equation (5).

$$\log \frac{C}{\theta} = \log C - \log K \quad (1)$$

$$\log \left((C) * \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \right) \right) = 2.303 \log K + 2\alpha\theta \quad (2)$$

$$\theta = - \frac{2.303 \log K}{2a} - \frac{2.303 \log C}{2a} \quad (3)$$

$$\log \left(\frac{\theta}{C} \right) = \log K + x \log (1 - \theta) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta G_{ads} = -2.303RT \log (55.5K) \quad (5)$$

where:

C (concentration of the inhibitor), K (adsorption equilibrium constant) and θ (degree of surface coverage), α (lateral interaction term), 'a' (attractive parameter), x (size parameter), R (gas constant, 8.314 kJ/kmol.K), T (absolute temperature).

2. 5. Response surface methodology (RSM)

On response surface methodology, central composite design tool of Design Expert Software (version 12) was used to design the experiment. Inhibitor concentration, temperature and time were the considered factors while inhibition efficiency was the response of the study.

The RSM was used to analyze the response in line with previous reports [8, 17]. And optimum inhibition parameters were obtained using optimization tool of the Design Expert Software.

2. 6. Electrochemical Studies

Electrochemical (potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy) studies were done according to the method used by previous studies [8, 19, 20]. The experiment was carried out using potentiostat/galvanostat 263 electrochemical system workstation, with a conventional three-electrode corrosion cell. A graphite rod and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) were used as a counter and reference electrodes, respectively. Mild steel sample fixed in epoxy resin with a surface area of 1 cm² served as the working electrode. Electrochemical measurements were carried out in aerated and unstirred solution at the end of 1800 s of immersion. It allowed the open circuit potential (OCP) to achieve steady state [8]. The temperature of the system was fixed at 30±1 °C.

2. 7. Scanning Electron Microscopic Analysis of the Mild Steel Surface

Mild steel samples were immersed in H₂SO₄, in the presence and absence of the inhibitor. At the end of the corrosion study, the mild steel samples were collected and studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM – model: Rhenom Prox, Phenom World Eindhoven, Netherlands).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Characteristics of the Inhibitor (Drug)

Figure 1. FTIR spectrum of Antepsin

The FTIR spectrum of antepsin is presented in Fig. 1. The peaks represent the functional group of the inhibitor [17]. The spectrum showed that C=O stretch, C-H bend and symmetric

and asymmetric =C-O-C as major functional groups of antepsin. The presence of the heteroatoms depicts that antepsin will be a good corrosion inhibitor [10, 17, 21]. The GCMS revealed the presence of tetradecanoate, metronidazole, hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester and 11-octadecenoic acid. Other constituents include heptadecanoic acid, 16-methyl-methyl ester, methyl stearate and bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate.

3. 2. Gravimetric results

Gravimetric results are presented in Tables 1 - 3. Weight loss and corrosion rate of mild steel in uninhibited H₂SO₄ were very high compared to those of inhibited H₂SO₄. The absence of inhibitor may have warranted aggressive, irreversible and spontaneous deterioration of the mild steel through chemical or electrochemical reaction with the environment [10, 15]. Inhibition efficiency and degree of surface coverage increased with increase in concentration of inhibitor. Decreased corrosion rate corresponds with increase in inhibitor (antepsin) concentration. The corrosion rate reduced because molecules of antepsin were adsorbed on the mild steel surface. The inhibitor forms a compact barrier film, which prevents the diffusion of Fe²⁺ to the liquid/metal interface, while at the same time it inhibits the diffusion of SO₄²⁻ to the metal/liquid interface. The barrier becomes more protective as the number of antepsin molecules increases, thus preventing dissolution of the mild steel sample.

Table 1. Effect of time on corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin

Time (hr)	ΔW_0 (g)	CR ₀ (mg/cm ² hr)	ΔW_1 (g)	CR ₁ (mg/cm ² hr)	IE (%)	Θ
1.0	0.15	12.500	0.05	4.167	66.67	0.6667
2.0	0.36	15.000	0.06	2.500	83.33	0.8333
3.0	0.55	15.278	0.07	1.944	87.27	0.8727
4.0	0.57	11.875	0.08	1.667	85.96	0.8596
5.0	0.59	9.8333	0.09	1.500	84.75	0.8475

Table 2. Effect of concentration on corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin.

Inh. Conc. (g/L)	ΔW_0 (g)	CR ₀ (mg/cm ² hr)	ΔW_1 (g)	CR ₁ (mg/cm ² hr)	IE (%)	Θ
0.0	0.55	15.278				
0.2			0.27	7.500	50.91	0.5091
0.4			0.21	5.833	61.82	0.6182

0.6			0.11	3.056	80.00	0.8000
0.8			0.07	1.944	87.27	0.8727
1.0			0.08	2.222	85.45	0.8545

Table 3. Effect of temperature on corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin.

Temp. (K)	ΔW_0 (g)	CR ₀ (mg/cm ² hr)	ΔW_1 (g)	CR ₁ (mg/cm ² hr)	IE (%)	Θ
303	0.51	14.167	0.09	2.5	82.35	0.8235
313	0.55	15.278	0.07	1.944	87.27	0.8727
323	0.58	16.111	0.14	3.889	75.86	0.7586
333	0.62	17.222	0.17	4.722	72.58	0.7258
343	0.64	17.778	0.20	5.556	68.75	0.6875

3. 3. Adsorption isotherm

The experimental data were fitted into Langmuir, Temkin, Frumkin and Flory-Huggins adsorption isotherms. Obtained adsorption isotherm parameters are presented in Table 4. Langmuir isotherm gave the highest values of correlation coefficient (R²), indicating that Langmuir adsorption isotherm is the most fitted [13]. From the Frumkin adsorption parameters, the lateral interaction term (α) presented positive values suggesting attractive behaviour of antepsin molecules on the mild steel surface. From the Temkin adsorption parameters, the attractive parameter values (a) were negative, showing that repulsion exists in the adsorption layer [7]. Positive values of size parameter (x) of Flory-Huggins implied that adsorbed molecule of antepsin was bulky [7, 13, 18]. The values of ΔG_{ads} are negative and less than the threshold value of -40000 J/mol. Thus, adsorption of the inhibitor is spontaneous as well as a physical adsorption process. Mechanism of action of a corrosion inhibitor may be connected to the electron density and polarization of the functional groups in the molecular species [20].

Table 4. Adsorption parameters for the corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin

Adsorption Isotherm	Temperature (K)	R ²	K	ΔG_{ads} (J/mol)	Isotherm property
Langmuir Isotherm	313	0.9829	1.1051	-10713.8	
	323	0.9803	1.3253	-11544.1	

Temkin Isotherm	313	0.9382	38.6189	-19963.4	a	-2.0540
	323	0.8859	60.3254	-21799.2		-2.7476
Frumkin Isotherm	313	0.9882	14.1971	-17358.8	α	1.9543
	323	0.969	12.8263	-17640.7		1.9976
Flory-Huggins Isotherm	313	0.8252	3.4245	-13657.5	x	0.628
	323	0.7263	3.8842	-14432.2		1.1514

3. 4. Results of the Response Surface Methodology

Table 5 showed maximum inhibition efficiency of antepsin as 92.45% at inhibitor concentration of 0.8g/L, temperature of 313K and time of 3hrs. The recorded high inhibition efficiency showed that antepsin is a suitable additive that can be used for pickling of mild steel structure.

Table 5. RSM results of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin.

Std	Run	Factor 1 A: Inhibitor conc. g/L	Factor 2 B: Temperature K	Factor 3 C: Time Hr	Response 1 Inhibition efficiency %
6	1	1.0	303	5	78.45
5	2	0.6	303	5	61.52
18	3	0.8	313	3	92.45
17	4	0.8	313	3	92.45
15	5	0.8	313	3	92.45
12	6	0.8	323	3	82.14
11	7	0.8	303	3	87.76
3	8	0.6	323	1	49.03
13	9	0.8	313	1	76.92
20	10	0.8	313	3	92.45
7	11	0.6	323	5	57.12
19	12	0.8	313	3	92.45
8	13	1.0	323	5	65.00

9	14	0.6	313	3	83.02
10	15	1.0	313	3	90.57
1	16	0.6	303	1	53.77
2	17	1.0	303	1	57.24
16	18	0.8	313	3	92.45
4	19	1.0	323	1	53.01
14	20	0.8	313	5	85.96

3. 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the Mathematical model

The ANOVA for corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin is presented in Table 6. It revealed model F-value as 110.29, which showed that the model is significant. There is only a 0.01% chance that F-value this large could occur due to noise. P-values less than 0.0500 indicate that the model terms are significant. The predicted R² of 0.9322 is in reasonable agreement with the adjusted R² of 0.9810; the difference is less than 0.2.

Table 6. ANOVA for corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	4364.98	9	485.00	110.29	< 0.0001	Significant
A-Inhibitor concentration	198.20	1	198.20	45.07	< 0.0001	
B-Temperature	191.23	1	191.23	43.49	< 0.0001	
C-Time	384.28	1	384.28	87.38	< 0.0001	
AB	2.43	1	2.43	0.5528	0.4743	
AC	122.70	1	122.70	27.90	0.0004	
BC	35.49	1	35.49	8.07	0.0175	
A ²	119.39	1	119.39	27.15	0.0004	
B ²	284.10	1	284.10	64.60	< 0.0001	
C ²	509.69	1	509.69	115.90	< 0.0001	
Residual	43.98	10	4.40			

Lack of Fit	43.98	5	8.80		
Pure Error	0.0000	5	0.0000		
Cor Total	4408.95	19			
Std. Dev.	2.10		R ²		0.9900
Mean	72.92		Adjusted R ²		0.9810
C.V. %	2.88		Predicted R ²		0.9322
			Adeq Precision		26.1990

The mathematical model of the inhibition efficiency of antepsin for corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ medium is expressed by Equation 6. It is a quadratic equation showing the interactive effects of the corrosion control variables on the inhibition efficiency.

$$IE = + 88.11 + 4.45A - 4.37B + 6.20C - 0.5513AB + 3.92AC - 2.11BC - 6.59A^2 - 10.16B^2 - 13.61C^2 \quad (6)$$

3. 6. Graphical analyses of the inhibition efficiency (IE)

Figure 2. Predicted versus actual inhibition efficiency of antepsin for mild steel in H₂SO₄

Figure 3. Inhibition efficiency versus inhibitor concentration and temperature

Figure 4. Inhibition efficiency versus inhibitor concentration and time

Figure 5. Inhibition efficiency versus temperature and time

In Figure 2, plot of predicted versus actual inhibition efficiency showed a linear graph. The points clustered along the line of best fit, indicating that the generated model can adequately predict the experimental result. This observation is in line with previous reports [7, 8]. Figures 3-5 show the interactive effect of inhibitor concentration, temperature and time on the inhibition efficiency. It revealed that IE increased with increase in inhibitor concentration till it got to the peak, where decline in trend was noticed.

The graphs revealed parabolic curves with 86.75% as optimum inhibition efficiency. Generated optimum inhibition efficiency was validated by comparing it with the experimental result of 87.74%. Percentage deviation of 1.13% was recorded, showing that the model adequately predicted inhibition efficiency of antepsin for corrosion control of mild steel in H_2SO_4 medium. High inhibition efficiency of antepsin may be due to its heteroatoms and structural compositions. With heteroatoms, corrosion inhibitor exhibits its character in an aggressive environment by obstructing invasion of electrochemical reactions [10, 15]. The inhibitor possess polar functional groups and structural multiple bonds (double and triple) that acted as adsorption centers during mild steel-inhibitor interactions in the H_2SO_4 medium.

3. 7. Results of Electrochemical Studies

Results of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and potentiodynamic polarization are presented in Figures 6 and 7 respectively. The antepsin (inhibitor) was designated by AS. Electrochemical impedance spectra of mild steel in H_2SO_4 medium in the absence and presence of antepsin are shown in Figure 6. The spectra are in three categories; Nyquist, Bode phase angle and Bode mag plots. In each of the plots, trend curves of uninhibited and inhibited H_2SO_4 with 0.6g/L and 0.8g/L antepsin were presented.

Figure 6. Electrochemical impedance spectra of mild steel in: (a) Nyquist and (b) Bode phase angle and (c) Bode mag plots in H₂SO₄ solution in the absence and presence of AS.

Table 7. Electrochemical parameters for mild steel in H₂SO₄ in the absence and presence of antepsin

System	R _s (Ω cm ²)	R _{ct} (Ω cm ²)	N	IE (%)	E _{corr} (mV)	I _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	IE%
H ₂ SO ₄	1.578	39.7	0.88		- 468.5	325.2	
H ₂ SO ₄ with 0.6 g/L AS	2.321	132.4	0.89	70.0	- 461.2	84.7	74.0
H ₂ SO ₄ with 0.8 g/L AS	2.332	174.6	0.89	77.3	- 458.6	55.4	83.0

The displayed semi-circle is an indication that there is a charge transfer process occurring with charge transfer resistance in parallel with the interfacial capacitance. Large charge transfer

resistance has direct relationship with slowly corroding system [8, 22]. It was revealed that addition of antepsin to the H_2SO_4 medium enhanced the magnitude of the impedance spectrum. It signifies the inhibiting strength of the constituents of the inhibitor which impeded the invading of electrochemical reactions. Table 7 presents the electrochemical parameter of mild steel in H_2SO_4 in the absence and presence of antepsin. Maximum value of inhibition efficiency of antepsin was recorded as 83% at concentration of 0.8g/L.

Figure 7 presents the potentiodynamic polarization curves. The polarization curves for the inhibition characteristics of the anodic and cathodic reactions were inhibited with the increase in inhibitor concentration. It depicts antepsin as a mixed type inhibitor because the curves shifted in both cathodic and anodic side. That is, polarization measurements showed that antepsin can be used to control both anodic and cathodic corrosions. The observation corroborates with the reports that mixed type inhibitor is useful in controlling anodic and cathodic corrosion [7, 19, 22].

Figure 7. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of mild steel in H_2SO_4 in the absence and presence of antepsin

3. 8. Results of the SEM Analyses

The micrographs of the mild steel samples in the H_2SO_4 medium in the presence and absence of the inhibitor are presented in Figures 8 and 9 respectively. There was significant difference in the morphology of the mild steel surface in the presence and absence of antepsin. The electron micrographs showed that the mild steel surface was strongly damaged owing to corrosion in the absence of the inhibitor, but in the presence of inhibitor there is a much smaller

damage. This can be attributed to the formation of a good protective film on the surface of the mild steel. The micrographs have close correlation with the results obtained from the weight loss method. This is in agreement with the previous studies [17, 23-26].

Figure 8. SEM Analysis of mild steel in H₂SO₄

Figure 9. SEM Analysis of mild steel in H₂SO₄ with antepsin

4. CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the results showed that major constituents of antepsin include tetradecanoate, metronidazole, hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester and 11-octadecenoic acid. The predominant functional groups include; C=O stretch, C-H bend and symmetric and asymmetric =C-O-C. Antepsin has polar functional groups with structural multiple bonds (double and triple) that acted as adsorption centers during the interaction of the mild steel and inhibitor.

Thermodynamic results revealed that the adsorption of molecules of antepsin on the surface of the mild steel was spontaneous and occurred according to the mechanism of physical adsorption. A quadratic model showing the relationship between inhibition efficiency and corrosion control variables of inhibitor concentration, temperature and time was obtained. Optimum inhibition efficiency of antepsin was obtained as 86.75%.

Chemical and electrochemical results are in agreement that antepsin is suitable for corrosion control of mild steel in H₂SO₄ solution. The inhibitor inhibited both cathodic and anodic reactions and acted as mixed-type inhibitor. Surface-nature of the mild steel samples in the presence and absence of the inhibitor confirmed that antepsin is an effective corrosion inhibitor.

BIOGRAPHY

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